

FINANCIAL AID SCHEMES AND ACCESS FOR THE UNDERPRIVILEGED

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Abstract: A nation's worth is expressed in terms of its literacy rate. The higher the numbers are, the greater the prospects of modernization, urban civilization, secularism, and rights reserved to each individual is acted upon. Generalizing the need to provide education to every civilian residing in a nation is his/her right, but the societal prejudice towards the lower economic strata has not gone unnoticed. Therefore, lakhs of children who want to avail their basic rights such as education are unable to do so due to the lack of adequate resources, awareness, accessibility, circumstantial restrictions, and low economic providence or financial instability. Due to this, the majority of the people lack decent qualifications, hence, remaining unemployed throughout causing there to be a high unemployment rate as well. To counter this intensity of incompetence, the Government of India has been taking numerous steps to facilitate the procurement of education. This is where financial schemes come into play encompassing various sectors, from UGC to AICTE, to scholarships/fellowships, and bank loans making it feasible for the underprivileged to not fall short. Apart from this, the older generation is found to be struggling with post-retirement benefits which are being catered to with additional government schemes and grants to provide them with a better life.

Keywords: Government schemes, accessibility, underprivileged, Scholarships, loans

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite every ADVANCEMENT made by humanity, many urban and rural residents still have low and often deteriorating quality of life [1]. The primary aim of providing the underprivileged with monetary benefits is to bridge the gap between their dreams and reality. These benefits not only help them overcome their financial deficit but their educational inadequacy as well. These monetary benefits are extended under the financial schemes provided by the Indian Government to uplift the lower strata and help them utilize their basic rights. Students interested in pursuing higher education are supposed to avail of these financial schemes. In many nations, it is common for the government to pay financial aid for students to boost enrolment and ensure everyone has access to higher education. Financial grants, often known as scholarships and fellowships, make up the majority of student financial support, others include work-study and loans [2]. More so, there are children who find it difficult to even go to school therefore for them, there are other schemes that enable them to pursue their elementary and high secondary education by going to schools.

These financial schemes can be availed for two different purposes at the same time or other depending on the need of the hour, i.e; educational loans or regular bank loans. Individuals can also avail for student loans which correspond to educational loans and help the students cover their tuition fees. Bank loans are generally availed to deal with living costs by keeping a collateral or a substantial property as mortgage taken up by the bank until the amount is returned with interest in the upcoming years within a definite time interval. However, these bank loans work differently for the underprivileged as it is understood that their financial condition is questionable. The Indian constitution, which is heavily in favor of the reservation system, is a disputed system. However, despite its many drawbacks, it seeks to offer assistance, including financial help, to individuals with minimal resources and money [3].

In India, the government provides for the basic needs of the poorer classes of society. In the future, The World Bank can be contacted if someone wants to pursue higher education in other nations. The World Bank Group is critical in increasing financial inclusion internationally by employing its understanding of the financial sector, country engagement and discussion, financing a, risk-sharing tools, special datasets and research capability, and financial sector experience. [4]. 1.2 billion adults globally gained access to an account between 2011 and 2017, which was a significant step toward financial inclusion. 69% of adults worldwide had accounts as of 2017. More than 80 countries have now adopted digital financial services, and some of them, particularly those that employ mobile devices, have grown a large industry. As a result, millions of uninsured persons and underserved low-income consumers of uninsured persons and underserved low-income consumers, as a result, use mobile phones or other digital technology in addition to cash for formal financial transactions [4,5].

The next phase for nations (like India) where 80% or more of the populace has accounts is the shift from accessibility to utilization. Reforms, business sector innovation, and a drive to establish low-cost accounts that accepted electronic and mobile payments were all important in these nations. Yet, 1.7 billion people, did not have a bank account in 2017, per the most available

Findex data. Women who hailed from low-income rural households or were unemployed hailed from low-income rural households or were unemployed made up about half of the unbanked population [5].

II. COMMON FINANCIAL AID AND SCHEMES

In order to improve the social and economic well-being of the nation's population, the government has undertaken a series of initiatives. The government periodically introduces new initiatives with predetermined goals. Most of these government programs are intended to aid the weaker members of society who may be in rural areas or economically disadvantaged areas. They primarily benefit low-income families and economically underprivileged or weaker segments of society. The main goals of these programs are to uplift the underprivileged sections of society, enhance living conditions, develop rural and underdeveloped areas, provide financial security, education, and training to the nation's most vulnerable citizens, and provide financial assistance to women, small businesses, and the most vulnerable sections of society. They also aim to encourage small-scale businesses by offering entrepreneurship and training opportunities [6].

2.1. Government loans and pensions

The Indian government has over the years implemented a number of programs that not just aided citizens enhance their financial conditions and improving the nation's economy, but they have also developed a number of unique pension programmes for older citizens to give them financial security and stability after retirement. After retiring, your income may be insufficient or very low. Paying for medical expenses and other necessities during such times can be difficult. This is where investing in a pension plan early can be a lifesaver [7,8]. While for many small enterprises, having a strong start with finance can be a blessing for the disadvantaged. The Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana, which aims to offer easily accessible financial services such as deposits, insurance, loans, and pensions., the Atal Pension Yojana (APY), which aims to reduce the risks of old age among workers in the unorganized sector and encourage them to actively contribute to their retirement, are a few of these programmes [9]. The other programs are listed in the table below (Table 1).

2.2. Elementary education

Many measures have been tried to increase the number of children enrolled in school because education is crucial for the development of a developing country like India. National development initiatives now include education as a crucial and vital component. The government has introduced numerous initiatives and programs to achieve the goal of universalizing elementary education, such as the mid meal programme, the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, which aims to educate all children between the ages of six and fourteen, and many others. (Table 1) [10-12].

2.3. Secondary and higher education

Some children are talented and brilliant academically but due to their financial backgrounds, they are unable to continue their education. The government and some organizations have started multiple initiatives like handing out scholarships and student loans to help support their dreams (Table 1) [11-13].

Table 1. Financial aid schemes and objectives

S.no	SCHEMES	AIMS/OBJECTIVES	LAUNCH YEAR
2.1. Government loans and pensions			
1.	Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY)	Aims to offer easily accessible financial services such as deposits, insurance, loans, and pensions.	August 2014
2.	Atal Pension Yojana (APY)	To address the risks associated with old age among unorganized sector workers and to motivate them to actively contribute to their retirement.	May 2015
3.	Pradhan Mantri Vaya Vandana Yojana (PMVVY)	Pensions exclusively for senior citizens aged 60 years and above	May 2017
4.	Stand Up India Scheme	To assist women and people from SC and ST areas with financial aid for starting greenfield businesses.	April 2016
5.	Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY)	To offer small/micro businesses that are neither corporations nor farms loans of up to 10 lakhs.	April 2015
6.	Credit Enhancement Guarantee Scheme (CEGS) for Scheduled Castes (SCs)	to encourage business owners who will make money, contribute to society, generate jobs, and build their confidence while also promoting successful enterprises.	July 2014
7.	Venture Capital Fund for Scheduled Castes under the Social Sector Initiatives	The SC entrepreneurs will receive financial help up to Rs. 15 crores for a period of up to 6 years.	2014-15
8.	Varishtha Pension Bima Yojana (VPBY)	Pensions exclusively for senior citizens aged 60 years and above	2017

2.2. Elementary Education			
9.	Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan	Intends to educate every child between the ages of six and fourteen.	2001
10.	Mid-day meal	This school meal program aims to improve the national nutrient intake of children in schools.	1962-63
11.	Mahila Samakhyā	To help educate women which can be an effective tool for women's empowerment.	1988
12.	Strengthening for providing quality Education in Madrassas (SPQEM)	Aims to increase the quality of minorities so that Muslim youngsters can meet the requirements for the formal education system at the national level.	2020-21
2.3. Secondary and Higher Education			
13.	Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA)	Aims to enhance access to secondary education and improve its quality and enrolment rates.	2009-10
14.	National Scheme of Incentives to Girls for Secondary Education	To create a positive environment that will lower dropout rates and encourage the admission of girls from SC/ST communities in secondary schools.	May 2008
15.	Inclusive Education for Disabled at Secondary Stage (IEDSS)	At the secondary level, give students with disabilities access to general education programs and facilities.	2009-10
16.	K.C. MAHINDRA Scholarship	The program targets students who have completed grades 10 and 12 or who have been admitted to diploma programs at government-approved institutions and have a low family income and insufficient funds to cover college expenditures.	1995
17.	Central Sector Scheme of Scholarship	The initiative helps students from low-income families pursue graduation and post-graduate goals while also taking care of everyday needs.	2008
18.	All India Council for Technical Education Scholarships	This program guarantees that students from financially disadvantaged households can pursue higher education while also offering financial help and critical amenities.	2014
19.	Innovation in Science Pursuit for Inspired Research (INSPIRE) fellowship	Each chosen applicant will receive a scholarship worth INR 80,000 per year to study science and technology and work in research.	2008
20.	National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme (NAPS)	To promote apprenticeship by providing financial incentives, technology, and advocacy support.	August 2016

III. FINANCIAL INCLUSION

The process of providing banking and financial services to every member of society without any kind of prejudice is known as financial inclusion. Without taking into account a person's income or savings, it essentially seeks to involve everyone in society by providing them with basic financial services [14]. The goal of financial inclusion is to lower the obstacles that prevent people from engaging with the financial system and utilising its products to better their lives. Additionally known as inclusive finance [15]. Financial inclusion is primarily concerned with giving trustworthy financial assistance to those in the economically disadvantaged parts of society without discrimination. It aims to offer financial solutions devoid of any indications of inequity [14]. The concept of financial inclusion encompasses more than just opening a bank account. Those who are banked could be denied access to financial services [16]. It is also dedicated to transparency while providing financial support without any additional fees or unexpected charges.

Everyone in society should be involved and take part in wise financial management, according to financial inclusion. In India, a lot of low-income families do not have any access to the nation's banking services. They are ignorant about banks' operations. Many poor people lack access to bank services, even when they are aware of them [14]. It is crucial that people with disabilities are recognized and included in development in order to provide inclusive and required support services for people with disabilities (including social protection aimed at full inclusion of people with disabilities). Included in this is funding that is sufficient for services and assistance related to disabilities [17]. They will not satisfy the basic eligibility requirements established by banks in which case they will be unable to seek a bank's services [14]. The government has financial inclusion as a top objective. The goal of financial inclusion is to increase access to financial services for the nation's sizable, previously underserved population in order to maximize its growth potential [18].

The minimum income, minimum credit score, age requirements, and limited years of work experience are just few of the conditions set by the banks. Only if an applicant satisfies these requirements will a bank provide him or her with a deposit or a loan. Due to a lack of resources, money, etc., many impoverished people may be unemployed and have no history of employment. These socially and economically handicapped people might also lack the mandatory documentation to present before

banks for identity or income facilitation. When applying for a loan or opening a bank account, each bank has a list of required documents that must be submitted. Many of these individuals are unaware of the significance of these texts. Additionally, they are unable to apply for official documentation. The aim of financial inclusion is to obliterate these hindrances and serve reasonably priced financial opportunities to the less fortunate segments of society so they can become financially independent without having to rely on charity or other undependable sources of funding [14]. The concept of contributing to the underprivileged, and developing economic resources are made more readily available as a result of financial inclusion [19]. The concept of financial inclusion is to observe a gradual increment in societal understanding of monetary services and management. Additionally, it will provide formal, organized channels for offering loans to the underprivileged [14].

For example, women still face appalling barriers to financial inclusion due to the gender gap. A 12% difference in bank account usage is reported by the 2021 Global Findex study, with many women using their accounts only for direct benefit transfers. According to numerous surveys, women make up fewer than 30% of retail borrowers, 14% of all credit that is outstanding, and 32% of people who own life insurance policies in India [20]. Only the middle and upper echelons of society were able to get formal forms of credit for a number of years. Poor people have little choice but to rely on illegitimate and unauthorized kinds of credit. As a result of their lack of education and basic financial skills, many of them were taken advantage of by opportunistic and wealthy members of society. Many low-income people have been taken advantage of for years in the name of financial aid [14]. Access to cheap financial products and services could be made easier with the aid of new technology [21].

IV. OBJECTIVES OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Financial inclusion will assist citizens in pertaining decent financial services and goods, such as deposits, fund transfer services, loans, insurance, payment services, etc. It attempts to formulate appropriate financial institutions that can meet the necessities of the underprivileged. These organizations ought to adhere to strict laws and standards in the financial sector. The goal of financial inclusion is to establish and maintain financial sustainability so that those who are less fortunate can count on having the money they need [14]. It aims to assist people in finding affordable financial goods and services. They include payments services, loans, insurance, and deposits [22]. To create just competition and give customers a variety of options, financial inclusion aims to have numerous organizations also, that provide cheaper financial help [14]. Access to a basic range of financial services, as well as opportunities for employment and skill development, are all provided [23]. The market offers conventional banking choices. However, there are surprisingly few institutions that provide low-cost financial goods and services. The goal of financial inclusion is to raise the benefits of financial services awareness among society's economically disadvantaged groups [14]. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a thorough empirical examination into the long-term effects of financial inclusion on Indian households and continuously monitor the development of new trends that have the potential to result in quantifiable welfare gains [24]. Financial inclusion aims to develop financial products that are appropriate for the less fortunate members of society. The goal of financial inclusion is to raise the country's level of financial knowledge and awareness [14]. Maximise your market - Bringing everyone under one roof is what financial inclusion entails. In the field of finance, it will assist in bringing together individuals and businesses from various backgrounds [25]. The goal of financial inclusion is to provide the nation's economically vulnerable citizens with digital financial solutions. In order to reach the most vulnerable citizens who reside in the most isolated regions of the nation, it also plans to introduce mobile banking or financial services [14]. The general populace's entrepreneurial spirit will be encouraged to improve outputs and wealth in rural areas if timely, appropriate, and transparent credit is readily available through official banking channels. The low-income and unbanked population, who are currently compelled to employ a variety of informal and expensive methods of sending money from one area to another, will be given access to formal remittance services- Facilities for remittances or money transfers, life-related microinsurance and other types of insurance (life and non-life) a little pension [26]. It attempts to give disadvantaged people specialized and personalized financial solutions based on their unique financial situations, household needs, preferences, and income levels [14]. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations represent the common objectives of nations and development agencies and go far beyond eradicating poverty. They take into account the need to conserve the environment while fostering wealth, human well-being, and the reduction of inequality [27]. Numerous governmental and non-governmental organizations are working to increase financial inclusion. These organizations are committed to facilitating the receipt of documents that have received official approval. Due to a lack of identification documentation, a large number of the poor are unable to open bank accounts or submit loan applications. There are a lot of people in rural areas and tribal settlements who are unaware of documents like PAN, Aadhaar, driver's licenses, and voter identification cards. As a result, individuals are unable to utilize many of the services provided by public or private institutions. They are unable to get any government assistance to which they are truly entitled since they lack these documents [14].

V. FINANCIAL INCLUSION FOR WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT

Women's empowerment is a radical approach to shifting power relations in favor of women, leading to improved gender equality [28]. Gender equality and women's empowerment are essential to global progress and can be strengthened by providing women with affordable financial services [29]. Women are more likely to have more productive and income-generating jobs if they have access to mobile banking services [30].

For example, one technical topic that came to mind recently is central bank digital currencies. The discussion of digital currency implementation summarizes the role of money in our society. In normal economic discourse, money is known to have three main functions: It is a store of value, a unit of account, and a medium of exchange. But the role of the money goes far beyond that. It especially affects our relationships on a family basis. We can define the dynamics of power in the home and economy. It can also determine the extent to which we influence our lives and personal choices. Often these relationships and dynamics play out in a gendered way. Architects of these new systems must therefore not only understand the macroeconomic implications and circulation of digital currencies but also consider the potential exclusion effects of replacing cash with digital currencies. Otherwise, we risk reinforcing existing social norms that disempower women. And the evidence base is fairly clear that if women cannot control their resources, they have little control over their lives and choices, a core aspect of their economic empowerment. and regardless of focus should be gender sensitive [31].

CGAP addresses formal and informal income opportunities for women because meeting their economic needs requires a differentiated understanding of their lives and livelihoods. We explore how social media-powered digital platforms and informal online commerce can help women, including women living in rural and farming communities, connect with new buyers and a more active market. Trying to understand and explore the role financial services can play in supporting women's participation and increasing their gains can help market system brokers and financial service providers to promote women's economic empowerment [32]. Financial inclusion is critical to economic growth and sustainable development. For women, it is the path to economic and social self-determination. Increased economic access for women has been shown to have a positive impact not only on women themselves, but also on their household income as a result [33]. G-20 countries are emphasizing financial inclusion as an enabler for achieving gender equality and other sustainable development goals. Women's empowerment is a fundamental approach that involves changing power relations in favor of women's gender and is seen as essential to global progress. A comprehensive financial model is put in place to achieve constructive goals [34].

According to UNESCO's Atlas on Gender Inequality in Education, around 10% of girls between the ages of 6 and 11 worldwide are denied the right to education, compared to 8% of boys. rights are denied. If current trends continue, about 16 million girls between the ages of 6 and 11 years old will miss out on primary school. A second obstacle is the practice of women often marrying against their will before their children become financially independent. This, along with early motherhood, makes her completely dependent on her husband or her in-laws. So when her husband loses his job or suffers a crop failure, her wife's life falls apart financially. Third, in many countries, women do not have the necessary ID cards without which they cannot access financial institutions. Fourth, in many developing and low-income countries women are not allowed to go to banks. Women are also often unable to control the wealth they own as it is controlled by their male relatives. Fifth, inheritance and marriage laws are another obstacle. In a patriarchal society, it is the son who inherits the property of his ancestors. However, many countries have now changed their laws or changed them to empower women. Finally, because women lack financial independence, it is difficult for credit bureaus to compile women's financial histories, preventing financial institutions from lending to them [35].

India launched Pradhan Mantri Jandhan Yojana (PMJDY) in 2014 to promote financial inclusion for all households in the country. The initiative aims to provide "economically excluded" people with access to financial services such as savings bank accounts, need-based loans, money transfers, insurance and pensions. Since then, more than 460 million bank accounts have been opened, according to the Ministry of Finance. 67% of these are in rural and suburban counties, and 56% are owned by women. The average amount deposited into PMJDY accounts nearly tripled from INR 1,279 in 2015 to INR 3,761 in 2022 [36]. According to 2021 Finance Ministry figures, the number of women beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana (10.26 million women) and Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana (3.42 million women) is increasing [37]. Between 2011 and 2021, the gender gap in account holders in developing countries narrowed from 9 percentage points to 6 percentage points. By 2021, 74% of men and 68% of women in developing countries had bank accounts [33]. When women have accounts in their own names and can use them safely, they are financially resilient, can save or access credit, and build a future for themselves and their families. means to prosper. Women can break the cycle of poverty and hunger and truly save and transform lives [38]. Inclusive growth is a prerequisite for India's economic development. Growth itself is short-lived unless all sectors of society reap the fruits of economic expansion. Countries are successfully implementing financial inclusion because there is strong political will to implement bold structural reforms and technology is working well towards that goal [39].

VI. THE IMPLICATIONS OF DEMONETIZATION

Demonetization had a strong positive effect on increasing financial inclusion compared to previous strategies. For example, the introduction of the Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) in 2014 coincided with a meager 34% rise in the percentage of the population holding a registered financial account over the period 2013-2016. obsolete. All demographic groups showed increased financial inclusion after abolition. A majority of nearly every demographic has made progress at every stage of the post-retirement customer journey. The only exception to this overall result is the lack of transition from active use to high active use among respondents living below the \$2.50 per day poverty line. bottom. Financial inclusion expanded fastest among women and rural residents [40]. After the demonetization, the use of financial services increased dramatically. There is a significant shift from non-users to users, increasing financial inclusion in the country [41].

Operationalized the Jan Dhan bank account with approximately 210 billion rupees (\$3 billion) in deposits. However, a new concept has been introduced called Benami Deposits. Jiang Dan's bank account, which was opened for the poorest people, has been swollen with cash since its abolition. This means that these accounts have become someone else's account holder. In detail, the impact of abolition on the process of financial inclusion in different parts of society involved in financial inclusion initiatives was explored [42]. On the night of November 8, 2016, the Government of India unveiled denomination Rs.500 and Rs.1000 banknotes. This means that these two denominations are denied legal tender status. The intention behind the demonstration was to curb black money and fight corruption and counterfeit money. However, this cannot be done overnight or in one or two drastic steps. Achieving a cashless economy is a complex process, requiring infrastructure support, financial literacy, cybersecurity, rules and regulations, availability of high-speed internet for the masses, more systems such as PMJDY, private and governmental involvement. and so on. Demonetization was seen as a change in behaviour, or a change in regime, that changed the age-old habit of people relying on cash to settle transactions [43]. As a result of the demonization, digital finance movements such as bank-provided e-money accounts, mobile banking, and peer-to-peer (P2P) lending banks have received widespread attention, and e-wallet companies have experienced rapid growth in terms of monetary transactions. Through web and app-based platforms [44]. Demonetization has led to an increase in financial intermediation [45].

Both the supply and demand sides of financial inclusion status are considered. Although this study did not find significant differences in switching costs or impacts on consumption and income between the included and excluded groups, it implicitly highlights the challenges of financial inclusion in rural economies [46]. Savings accounts help economically excluded people, most of whom are poor and illiterate, to store and build their transaction histories. This helps them access credit and invest in entrepreneurial ventures [47]. According to the Financial Inclusion Insights Survey, 49% of Indian adults are digitized. Significantly improved account usage and savings behaviour [48].

Financial Inclusion, End of Monetization and Digital India are three key elements of emerging India that will affect the Indian economy as a whole [49]. This can be more pronounced in rural areas where many people are non-agricultural Companies buy

fertile farmland not for farming, but for parking. Pause. The abolition of monetization and the consequent contraction of the informal economy reduce the demand for such arable land. This step should lead to something better tax collection. Inflation may be on a downtrend in the short term as cash transactions decline short term [50]. Mobile phone transactions grew exponentially from October 2016 to January 2020 (from 72.6 million to 1,440.3 million). In the last three years alone, the number of mobile banking transactions has grown nearly 20-fold, while the average mobile banking transaction size has slumped by a quarter (from Rs. 14,355 in October 2016 to 1 to Rs. 3,620 a month) [51]. The impact of deprecation is entirely dependent on supply and demand factors. The abolishment of cashing has affected most industries and consumers that rely on cash rather than non-cash, especially heterogeneous consumers, and will create a significant liquidity shock to India's macro-resilient production and prosperity causing it [52].

VII. WAYS TO AVAIL FINANCIAL INCLUSION

For those who are less fortunate, having access to money is crucial in the event of an unexpected disaster. Banks, payments networks, microfinance institutions, NGOs, telecommunications companies, technology businesses, and consumer goods corporations are just a few of the organizations that can all play a part in extending financial inclusion and providing assistance for them. [53]. To ensure that people are aware of the value of investing, saving, and financial planning, financial literacy must be promoted. Some strategies being used to ensure access to everyone include opening branches and sources of service in rural locations, concentrating on assisting women and low-income groups, lowering the minimum amount for accounts, etc [54]. Digitalization of the various monetary processes is an important factor to consider. In the future, the government intends to promote and improve the financial inclusion process using the Financial Inclusion Index provided by the RBI [55].

7.1. Digitalization

Digital financial inclusion entails using cost-effective digital methods to offer a range of official financial services that are appropriately delivered at a cost that is affordable for customers and viable for service providers to populations that lack employment opportunities and are financially exempt [56]. Financial and monetary system officials claim that this lowers the amount of actual cash in circulation and is essential in lowering high inflation rates in developing and undeveloped countries like India. The welfare of people and enterprises can be improved and the chance of being duped reduced by having a reliable digital platform to use to access money in their bank accounts [57,58]. The Indian government has released a number of smartphone applications that serve as electronic wallets, such as Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM), Aadhaar Pay, and others. Several digital financial instruments provide enticing bargains and discounts to customers who use them [59]. By inclusion through the digitalization of conventional banking, those who are underprivileged and marginalized in society may be able to access amenities like affordable healthcare, equitable education, opportunities for equal employment, and equality in income [60,61].

7.2. Microfinance and non-banking financial companies

By the financial service of microfinance, groups or individuals who are unemployed or have low incomes can access financial services that they would not otherwise have. It enables people to obtain fair small business loans in a secure manner that is in line with ethical lending norms [62]. When the government introduced the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana to assist micro-enterprises in 2015, microfinance institutions (MFIs) were selected as essential partners. Almost 60% of the credit offered under the Shishu subcategory of Mudra loans came from MFIs. It helps low-income families stabilise their fluctuating income and save money for upcoming expenses. Microfinance helps households and small businesses flourish in prosperous times and can support coping and restoration in difficult times [63]. Because many micro, small, and medium-sized firms (MSMEs) are led and run by women, these MFIs help rural women achieve financial independence and give them the power to make sensible decisions [64,65]. Many Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs) in India offer personal loans to people who need fast money to pay for personal expenses. The competitive personal loan interest rates offered by NBFCs range from close to 11% -36% per year. Borrowers frequently qualify for loans up to Rs. 25 lakhs or even greater. A few known NBFCs that provide loans are Tata Capital, Mahindra Finance, Aditya Birla Capital, HDB Financial Services, etc. [66,67].

7.3. Role of Reserve Bank of India (RBI)

The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and the government are crucial in fostering financial inclusion for economic progress in order to expand banking penetration, install new ATMs, and conduct various programs around the nation [68]. The following are a few of the initiatives:

- No frills account-Keeping a minimum balance of zero or a very low balance is required for this basic banking account.
- Basic savings bank deposit account (BSBDA)-There is no minimum balance option available for this account. The banks can use this account for a variety of activities, including cash deposits and withdrawals at bank branches. This is also possible at the appropriate bank ATMs [69].
- Lead banking scheme (LBS)
- PMJDY – Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana- The idea of opening a PMJDY account was well received throughout India, making banking accessible to the majority of the country's citizens. [70].
- Business correspondent system-These are the bank personnel who travel to the locations that are permitted to perform the necessary banking operations there [69].

The RBI has continuously urged the banking sector to increase the number of branches and ATMs in order to broaden the banking network [71]. The following is a list of the Financial Inclusion Strategy of the RBI: Policy Interventions A lending-friendly climate must be promoted, financial services must be made easier, cheaper, and more accessible, and cutting-edge goods must be used [72]. A few of the problems that restrict access to financial products include lack of awareness about them, high transaction

costs, pricey products, and low-quality, uncomfortable, stiff, and uncustomized products. Yet, we must remember that, in addition to supply-side constraints, demand-side problems, such as decreased income and/or asset holdings, also significantly affect inclusive growth. The success of this project depends on banks and other conventional financial institutions [73].

7.4. Private sector and financial technology (FINTECH)

Private businesses have also initiated efforts to assist the nation in achieving financial inclusion. These commercial companies, who created and implemented the programmes, encouraged low-income groups of people to take part in developmental projects. These programmes include Project Shakti from Hindustan Unilever, E-Choupal or E-Sagar from ITC, and the Haryali Kisan Bazaar from DCM [74]. The employment of cutting-edge technology in the financial sector or industry is referred to as financial technology (fintech) [75]. Fintech companies may play a big role in fostering financial inclusion by harnessing the current financial ecosystem and cutting-edge technologies to make banking for large numbers of impoverished and unbanked Indians easier, more accessible, and more inexpensive [76]. Using government support and initiatives is also facilitated by granting access to fundamental products and services, such as financing or savings tools [77]. The infrastructure of the Indian financial sector has significantly improved in recent years as a result of the launch of the Unified Payments Interface (UPI), Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM), and countless other financial services. It has gained even more pace with the establishment of the "Digital India" and "Made in India" initiatives, both of which are consistent with the RBI's objective of boosting the adoption of fintech. Demonetization has greatly sped up the growth of fintech in India [78]. FinTech, as it is commonly known, is a term used to describe "products and businesses that use recently developed internet-based and digital technologies in the financial services and banking industries," but its main objective is to fill the gaps in the financial needs of those segments of the population that are not the main target audiences for conventional financial services models. In order to assist the larger goal of financial inclusion, fintech was developed [79].

VIII. CASE STUDIES

8.1. Loans for small businesses

Meera

Low-caste women in a tiny town in Rajasthan State, India, hardly ever sit comfortably in their businesses and conduct business on their phones. Her company, "Matching and Sewing Centers," serves as an example to others in her generation. Few people in the town can match Meera, 30, who has three kids enrolled in elite schools. Since 2006, Meera has received assistance from Planned Social Concern (PSC) to help her succeed as an entrepreneur and eighth-grade student. Now on her fourth \$475 business loan cycle with PSC, Meera is certain that she will soon pay it off. Nonetheless, up until five years ago, Meera was just another neighbouring woman struggling to get by with a sick husband (a fatal case of TB), a strict mother-in-law, and three hungry, illiterate kids. She currently runs a modest business while giving free sewing lessons to young girls. Her life has been altered by the loan cycles, which have given her trust and confidence. She obtained her first loan to buy an electric sewing machine to expand her business, followed by an inverter to shield her stitching from the erratic power supply, and she is currently taking motorbike riding lessons to increase her mobility. She believes that her driving force was to give her children a nice life and prevent them from going through what she did. She and her healthy husband put forth a lot of effort to accumulate money for their kids' future education and a better life. [79].

8.2. Pension schemes for elders

8.2.1. Laxmi sellar

Laxmi Shellar's father unexpectedly took her out of 7th grade and married her to a 65-year-old as his second wife at 13. Her first son was born through caesarean at 14 because her hips were too narrow. She fell pregnant again at 16 while her husband was paralysed. Laxmi, a hugely pregnant 17-year-old, was widowed. "Laxmi," "17-year-old me was alone. I could either start again or commit suicide." Laxmi embraced life, rising to prominence in a culture that had shunned the young widow. Laxmi has lived in her late husband's home with his first wife, cultivating and selling his land, since his death [80]. Laxmi works in the field, sells vegetables at local markets, raises buffalo, sells their milk door-to-door, and organises her 10 SHGs with Mann Vikas Mahila Bank [81]. Laxmi has used numerous Mann Vikas programmes. She says Marathi women always work hard and suffer, so the chance to purchase a goat or buffalo and build assets is a little but significant change. They may prioritise their children's health and education with the increased revenue. [82] She understood the Mann Vikas/UTI pension programme instantly, adding, "Save for the future. We may donate our pension when we're too elderly to work. This will also help us manage our old-age medical costs." Years of relying on her have taught Laxmi this standard answer. Laxmi recognises the value of a pension after years of hard physical effort. Ladies like Laxmi make the Mann Vikas/UTI Pension Plan succeed. Laxmi's assistance, encouragement, and recordkeeping as a SHG leader enable Mann Vikas increase membership and assure payments. Laxmi concludes, "See my life. My life? Life is unsatisfying. I receive the greatest joy from helping ladies who have never gone to school or the bank acquire loans and animals they manage. Helping these ladies mature independently would also satisfy me." [80]

8.2.2 Tribals of arunachal pradesh

In order to prevent old age poverty, the old age pension evens out lifetime income. Seniors from tribal groups can make their own budgets by having their money redistributed. Elderly tribal members should be treated as capable adults who can manage their money if they are to be given permission to spend their monthly government payments on themselves and their families. Economic units prefer smooth consumption, which distributes predicted income across a lifetime, according to economic theory and empirical evidence. There are two ways to smooth household wellbeing. First, careful job and production choices as well as economic diversification assist stabilise family income. Second, employing formal and informal risk-sharing agreements, borrowing and saving, accumulating and disposing of assets, changing the labour supply (including their children), and changing asset ownership

can all help to smooth consumption. The tools supplied by the government for smoothing consumption allowed the tribal elderly to largely regulate their way of life. Elders in the tribe are shielded from economic instability, which precludes risk adaptation, through income smoothing. However, in the absence of effective market-based or government-provided consumption-smoothing tools, adverse income shocks frequently result in expensive informal coping mechanisms like dropping children from school, cutting back on nutrition, selling productive assets, and skipping the development of human capital. Tribal elders who are poor and at the end of their rope tend to be risk-averse. Due to inadequate consumption smoothing and risk aversion mechanisms, households will select low-risk, low-yield activities [83].

8.3 Education financing

8.3.1 Akanksha foundation

Most Indians are ignorant. Poor families, marginalised groups, and millions in poverty cannot afford basic education for their children. Even if they can, it is not a priority when families are struggling to provide two square meals and a home. It makes education a luxury. To bridge this gap, Akanksha Schools provide excellent education to underprivileged pupils, but after Grade 10, they must continue their education through college to escape the cycle of poverty and choose a job. Namrata Khanvilkar excelled in Acharya Vinoba Bhave School in Pune and continues to lead as an Akanksha alumni. St. Olaf College in Minnesota granted her a full scholarship in 2017. She also attended UWC Armenia on a full scholarship for two years. Namrata is Akanksha's first American college student. Akanksha's Abhyudaya Nagar Mumbai Public School accepted five-year-old Suraj. He has modest roots. Mother was a housewife and father sold veggies. Both his parents valued education and pushed their children to study. Suraj engaged in many school activities and interacted with many individuals. This gave him a large network and confidence. Suraj's grade 2 teacher, Mr. Yash, has been his life coach for years. He brought them to IIT, where Suraj realised his long-term goals. Suraj got into IIT Kharagpur after months of struggle. Akanksha School and its staff empower underprivileged pupils [84,85].

8.3.2 Google scholarship

Surondesh Daulagupu

Assam's Langting is Surondesh Daulagupu's hometown. His life was troubled by 11th grade. Addiction caused his 12th board exam failure. He couldn't correct his mistakes, and his scorecard didn't qualify him for a reputable undergraduate institution. Surondesh had an epiphany—he knew he needed to break away from his past and his issues. He self-taught Android coding via Udacity. New abilities boosted his confidence. He won a Google Developer Scholarship after trying! He's practising Android development and hoping for a decent career. Surondesh proves change is possible.

Rajani M

Rajani distinguishes out among the many great Google Developer Scholarship students. The oldest individual to get one of these chances, she is an inspiration. Rajani supported her mother financially when her father died. She worked hard, but she wanted to have children, which would hurt her job. She knew she would work again, thus in 2016, she started her developer profession again. She persisted. Nevertheless, after two weeks, she had excruciating back pain that prohibited her from sitting, standing, or travelling. Bedrest again halted her career. Despite the challenges, she persevered and took advantage of an Udacity Google Scholarship to progress her profession without harming her health. She's an Android specialist

Ruhan Khandaker

Family responsibilities prohibited Ruhan from attending college. No technical training or degree. Ruhan was undeterred. He was confident and motivated to develop a technological career. He went to Udacity to learn Python programming because of his drive. He liked learning and looked for new chances. He saw the Google Developer Scholarship as a way to further his career. Ruhan is in Phase 2 of the scholarship programme. He's also teaching scholarship students new talents!

Piyush Kant Maav

Piyushkant Maav Piyush always wanted to code, but it seemed unlikely. His father made enough as a clothing store salesperson to feed the family. Piyush persisted. He thought he was capable and had possibilities. A small cybercafé taught him rudimentary programming. He built his first website in Class 10. Piyush wanted to go to a top institution, but a family emergency ruined their funds, forcing him to attend a small engineering school. He learned more, but he ran out of resources to improve. The Google Developer Scholarship was his ideal opportunity. After receiving the Google Scholarship, his work ethic has astonished everyone, and he is one of the most active contributors in the Front-End Developer track [86].

IX. CONCLUSION

In this review paper, we have discussed about the various types of financial aid schemes available for people and how they can be availed by different methods. Financial inclusion has been a boon for the “Digital-India Scheme” as the process of digitalization has caught up with a pretty good pace making e-commerce come to life. Be it through digitalization solely, or microfinancing, the RBI or the private sectors, providing financial aid has never been easier. Especially with every gender being equally satisfied with the services being provided and there's also been a surge noticed in case of women using digital interfaces even more so than men as shown in the statistics. This is has not only been of national but global priority as well. Over the years, the underprivileged have been made to open their bank accounts by the government to fend for themselves and not be alien to the modern world. Even the onset of demonetisation affected financial inclusion in a positive way, digitalising transfers and maintaining confidentiality online.

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